

Studies in Metallic Complexes of Ethylenediamine Hydrochloride. Part I. Complex Formation between Vanadyl Sulphate and Ethylenediamine Hydrochloride

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Vanadyl sulphate forms a water-soluble complex with ethylenediamine hydrochloride. The composition of the complex, established spectrophotometrically and conductometrically by the application of Job's method of continued variations, has been found to be VOR_2 (R=reagent). The dissociation constant of the complex at 20° is 2×10^{-6} .

The ethylenediamine molecule, $H_2N-CH_2-CH_2-NH_2$, is remarkable for its power of forming a stable five-membered ring of the type

Chelates between ethylenediamine and trivalent transitional atoms such as Cr^{3+} (Rollinson and Bailar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 250), Fe^{3+} (Breuil, *Compt. rend.*, 1933, **196**, 2009), and Co^{3+} (Jaeger and Blumendal, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, **175**, 161) have been reported. With the divalent cupric atom, 6-covalent complexes of this kind are known, but a more usual and exceptionally stable (Job, *Compt. rend.*, 1927, **184**, 1066) type is the 4-covalent dichelate form. Such ring structures are also met with in the case of other bivalent metals, viz., Be^{2+} (Fricke and Havestadt, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, **152**, 357), Zn^{2+} , and Cd^{2+} (Hieber and Reindl, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1940, **46**, 556.)

Vanadium in vanadyl (VO^{2+}) state is known to give rise to 4-covalent complexes with bidentate ligands (Zolotavin and Kalugina, *Zhur. neorg. Khim.*, 1950, **1**, 703; Bhattacharya and Banerjee, *Curr. Sci.*, 1960, **29**, 147). The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the system vanadyl sulphate and ethylenediamine hydrochloride by using spectrophotometric, conductometric, and pH methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions of vanadyl sulphate (B.D.H.) and ethylenediamine hydrochloride (AnalaR) in conductivity water were used. The vanadium (IV) content of the vanadyl sulphate solution was estimated before use by means of ammonium benzoate as a precipitant (Shemyakin and Chapuigin, *J. Appl. Chem., U.S.S.R.*, 1935, **8**, 536). Beckman spectrophotometer, Doran conductivity bridge, and glass electrode pH meter were used for optical density, conductance, and pH measurements, respectively. The measurements were carried out at a constant temperature of $20^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Nature of the Complex Formed

The absorption spectra of mixtures of equimolar solutions ($M/10$) of vanadyl sulphate and the reagent in the ratios of 1:1, 1:2, and 1:3 were studied. The nature of the curves (Fig. 1, curves A, B, & C) is identical; moreover, they do not intersect each other, thus indicating the probability of the formation of only one complex. The curves show maxima at the wave length of about 775 $m\mu$. For further study, the optical density measurements were taken at or near this wave length.

FIG. 1. Variation of O. D. with $m\mu$.

A : 1:1 mixture
 B : 1:2 „
 C : 1:3 „

FIG. 2. Comp. of the complex by monovariation method.

A : 775 $m\mu$.
 B : 750 $m\mu$.

The nature of the complex has been further studied by the application of monovariation method (Nayar and Pandey, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 284). Only one break, at 1:2 ratio, is seen in the curves obtained from optical density (Fig. 2, curves A & B), conductance, and pH (Fig. 3, curves A & B) measurements showing the formation of only one complex.

Effect of H^+ Ion Concentration on the Absorption of Light

The absorbance of a mixture of equimolar ($M/10$) vanadyl sulphate and ethylenediamine hydrochloride in the ratio of 1:2 at wave length 775 $m\mu$ was noted over a pH range of 2 to 5. The results indicate that the colour intensity reaches a maximum at pH 4 and then decreases at higher pH values. Therefore optical measurements were taken with solutions having pH 4.

Ethylenediamine HCl (c.c.).

FIG. 3 Composition of the complex by monovariation method.

A : by conductance.
B : by pH.

FIG. 4. Composition by Job's method.

A : at 775 m μ
B : ,, 750 ,,
C : ,, 800 ,,

FIG. 5. Composition (A) and diss. const. (B) of the complex.

Composition of the Complex by Job's Method: Spectrophotometric Study

The composition of the complex formed was determined by Job's method of continued variation (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, *x*, 9, 113), using *M*/10 solutions each of vanadyl sulphate and ethylenediamine hydrochloride. The optical densities were noted at wave lengths 750 m μ , 775 m μ , and 800 m μ . In all the cases the maxima in the curves plotted (Fig. 4, curves A, B, & C)

between the difference in optical density and percentage of ethylenediamine hydrochloride were obtained at 66% ethylenediamine hydrochloride, indicating the formation of a 1:2 complex.

Conductometric Study.—The stoichiometry of the complex formed was confirmed by the application of Job's method (*loc. cit.*) to conductance measurements using equimolar ($M/40$) solutions of vanadyl sulphate and ethylenediamine hydrochloride. The curve (Fig. 5, curve A) exhibits a maximum at 66% of ethylenediamine hydrochloride, establishing the stoichiometry of the complex as obtained from optical density measurements.

The dissociation constant of the complex formed was determined by conductometric measurement using nonequimolar solutions ($M/60$ vanadyl sulphate and $M/40$ ethylenediamine hydrochloride) in continued variation method.

DISCUSSION

The stoichiometry of the complex formed indicates that one molecule of vanadyl sulphate reacts with two molecules of ethylenediamine hydrochloride and it is represented as

The dissociation constant of the complex formed was calculated by substitution of the values in Job's simplified equation:

$$K = \frac{C^2 \cdot P [(P+2)x-2]^3}{(P-1)^2 \cdot (2-3x)}$$

where C = concentration of the metal solution, P = concentration of the ligand, and x = fraction of the ligand used. Thus, $C = M/60 = 0.01667$; $P = (M/40) / (M/60) = 1.5$; $x = 0.59$ (Fig. 5, curve B). The value of the dissociation constant K is found to be 2×10^{-6} at 20° .

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